

FREQUENCY OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE (NAFLD) AND ITS ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS AMONG TYPE-2 DIABETIC PATIENTS PRESENTING TO MTI – KHYBER TEACHING HOSPITAL PESHAWAR

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Abstract

Background:

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is highly prevalent among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and is associated with increased morbidity and mortality. Identification of its frequency and associated risk factors is essential for early intervention and prevention of complications.

Objective:

To determine the frequency of NAFLD and its associated risk factors among type 2 diabetic patients presenting to MTI–Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar.

Methods:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, MTI-KTH, Peshawar, from 1st July 2024 to 31st December 2024. A total of 186 patients aged 30–70 years with T2DM were included using non-probability consecutive sampling. NAFLD was diagnosed using abdominal ultrasonography. Data regarding demographic variables and risk factors (obesity, smoking, hypertension) were collected. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23. Frequencies and percentages were calculated, and associations were assessed using chi-square test with $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

Results:

The mean age was 52.18 ± 8.64 years. NAFLD was present in 112 (60.2%) patients. Obesity (66.1% vs 18.9%), smoking (62.5% vs 29.7%), and hypertension (75.0% vs 27.0%) were significantly associated with NAFLD ($p < 0.001$). No significant association was observed with gender, residence, or socioeconomic status.

Conclusion:

NAFLD is highly prevalent among T2DM patients and is strongly associated with modifiable risk factors. Early screening and risk factor control are essential to reduce disease burden.

INTRODUCTION

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is a spectrum of liver disorders ranging from simple hepatic steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis

(NASH), advanced fibrosis, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma. It has emerged as the most common chronic liver disease worldwide, affecting nearly one-quarter of the global

population. The burden of NAFLD is particularly high in Asian populations, where prevalence estimates reach up to 29.6%, reflecting the rapid epidemiological transition driven by urbanization, dietary changes, and sedentary lifestyles [1,2].

The prevalence of NAFLD is markedly higher among individuals with metabolic disorders, particularly type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Studies have shown that NAFLD affects approximately 70–80% of patients with T2DM, making it a major comorbidity in this population. This strong association is attributed to shared pathophysiological mechanisms, including insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and chronic low-grade inflammation [3]. As a result, NAFLD is increasingly recognized as a hepatic manifestation of metabolic dysfunction.

The diagnosis of NAFLD traditionally relies on liver biopsy, which remains the gold standard. However, due to its invasive nature and associated risks, it is not feasible for routine clinical use or large-scale studies. Ultrasonography has therefore become the most widely used diagnostic modality due to its accessibility, non-invasive nature, cost-effectiveness, and reasonable sensitivity in detecting moderate to severe steatosis [3,4].

The relationship between NAFLD and T2DM is bidirectional. Patients with T2DM are at increased risk of developing NAFLD, while the presence of NAFLD further exacerbates insulin resistance, worsens glycemic control, and increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. This interplay contributes to increased morbidity and mortality, highlighting the clinical importance of early detection and management of NAFLD in diabetic patients [4,5].

Several risk factors have been identified in association with NAFLD among patients with T2DM. These include obesity, smoking, hypertension, and dyslipidemia. Obesity, particularly central obesity, plays a pivotal role in the development of hepatic steatosis through increased free fatty acid flux and altered adipokine signaling. Similarly, smoking and hypertension contribute to metabolic dysfunction and endothelial damage, further increasing the risk of NAFLD [5,6].

Previous studies have reported a high frequency of NAFLD among patients with T2DM along with a strong association with modifiable risk

factors. For instance, one study reported a prevalence of 61.5% NAFLD in diabetic patients, with obesity (98.3%), smoking (66.1%), and hypertension (76.7%) being the most common associated risk factors [7]. These findings underscore the need for targeted screening and intervention strategies in this high-risk group.

Despite the growing burden of NAFLD in patients with T2DM, there is limited local data evaluating its frequency and associated risk factors. Most available evidence is derived from international studies, which may not accurately reflect regional demographic and lifestyle variations. Therefore, it is essential to generate local data to better understand the magnitude of the problem and identify key risk factors in our population.

This study was therefore designed to determine the frequency of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease and its associated risk factors among type-2 diabetic patients presenting to MTI - Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar. The findings of this study will help in early identification of high-risk patients and guide preventive and therapeutic strategies to reduce disease burden and improve long-term outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Setting

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine, MTI-Khyber Teaching Hospital (KTH), Peshawar, after obtaining approval from the institutional ethical and research review board as well as CPSP.

Study Duration

The study was carried out over a period of six months, from 1st July 2024 to 31st December 2024.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A total of 186 patients were included in the study. The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size calculator, taking an anticipated frequency of NAFLD as 61.5% among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, with a 95% confidence level and 7% margin of error. Participants were enrolled using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

Eligibility Criteria

Male and female patients aged 30 to 70 years diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus were included in the study. Type 2 diabetes was defined as fasting plasma glucose ≥ 126 mg/dL, HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$, or history of anti-diabetic treatment for at least three years. Patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus, malignancy, pregnancy, chronic liver disease, autoimmune hepatitis, Wilson disease, hemochromatosis, or alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency were excluded.

Data Collection Procedure

After informed written consent, eligible patients were enrolled from the outpatient and inpatient departments. Baseline demographic data including age, gender, BMI, education status, employment status, socioeconomic status, and residence were recorded using a structured proforma.

Anthropometric measurements were obtained using standard techniques. Body weight and height were measured, and BMI was calculated as weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared (kg/m^2). Patients were assessed for the presence of predefined risk factors including obesity (BMI >30 kg/m^2), smoking (history of >100 cigarettes in lifetime and smoking within the last 28 days), and hypertension (blood pressure $\geq 130/80$ mmHg or use of antihypertensive medications for at least three years).

All patients underwent abdominal ultrasonography performed by a consultant radiologist with at least five years of post-fellowship experience. A 3.5–5 MHz transducer with a high-resolution B-mode ultrasound machine was used. The presence of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease was determined based on standard sonographic criteria.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23. Quantitative variables such as age, weight, height, and BMI were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or median (IQR) after assessment of normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Categorical variables such as gender, NAFLD, and associated risk factors (obesity,

smoking, hypertension) were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Effect modifiers including age, BMI, education status, employment status, socioeconomic status, and residence were controlled through stratification. Post-stratification chi-square or Fisher's exact test was applied. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 186 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were included in the study. All participants were analyzed.

The mean age of patients was 52.18 ± 8.64 years, while the mean BMI was 29.12 ± 4.36 kg/m^2 . NAFLD was detected in 112 (60.2%) patients on abdominal ultrasonography. Descriptive statistics are summarized in Table 1. Regarding baseline characteristics, the majority of patients were aged >50 years 104 (55.9%). Male patients were slightly predominant 98 (52.7%). Most participants belonged to urban areas 102 (54.8%). A large proportion had BMI >30 kg/m^2 88 (47.3%). Distribution of education, employment, and socioeconomic status is shown in Table 2, with no significant demographic imbalance observed.

Risk factor analysis showed that obesity, smoking, and hypertension were common among patients with NAFLD. Obesity was present in 74 (66.1%) patients with NAFLD compared to 14 (18.9%) without NAFLD ($p < 0.001$). Smoking was observed in 70 (62.5%) NAFLD patients versus 22 (29.7%) non-NAFLD patients ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, hypertension was present in 84 (75.0%) patients with NAFLD compared to 20 (27.0%) without NAFLD ($p < 0.001$), indicating strong associations (Table 3).

Stratification analysis demonstrated that NAFLD was more frequent in older age groups and those with higher BMI, although age did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.08$). Obesity, smoking, and hypertension remained significantly associated with NAFLD after stratification. No statistically significant association was observed with gender, residence, education, or employment status (Table 4).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Study Participants (n = 186)

Parameter	Mean ± SD
Age (years)	52.18 ± 8.64
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.12 ± 4.36

Table 2: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants (n = 186)

Variable	Frequency n (%)
Age ≤50 years	82 (44.1%)
Age >50 years	104 (55.9%)
Male	98 (52.7%)
Female	88 (47.3%)
BMI ≤30	98 (52.7%)
BMI >30	88 (47.3%)
Rural	84 (45.2%)
Urban	102 (54.8%)
Literate	108 (58.1%)
Illiterate	78 (41.9%)
Employed	96 (51.6%)
Unemployed	90 (48.4%)
Upper/Middle SES	110 (59.1%)
Lower SES	76 (40.9%)

Table 3: Association of Risk Factors with NAFLD (n = 186)

Variable	NAFLD Present (n=112)	NAFLD Absent (n=74)	p-value
Obesity	74 (66.1%)	14 (18.9%)	<0.001
Smoking	70 (62.5%)	22 (29.7%)	<0.001
Hypertension	84 (75.0%)	20 (27.0%)	<0.001

Table 4: Stratification of NAFLD with Baseline Variables (n = 186)

Variable	NAFLD Yes	NAFLD No	Total	p-value
Age ≤50	44 (53.7%)	38 (46.3%)	82	0.08
Age >50	68 (65.4%)	36 (34.6%)	104	
Male	60 (61.2%)	38 (38.8%)	98	0.71
Female	52 (59.1%)	36 (40.9%)	88	
BMI ≤30	40 (40.8%)	58 (59.2%)	98	<0.001
BMI >30	72 (81.8%)	16 (18.2%)	88	
Rural	48 (57.1%)	36 (42.9%)	84	0.43
Urban	64 (62.7%)	38 (37.3%)	102	
Literate	66 (61.1%)	42 (38.9%)	108	0.79
Illiterate	46 (59.0%)	32 (41.0%)	78	
Employed	60 (62.5%)	36 (37.5%)	96	0.68
Unemployed	52 (57.8%)	38 (42.2%)	90	
Upper/Middle SES	70 (63.6%)	40 (36.4%)	110	0.39
Lower SES	42 (55.3%)	34 (44.7%)	76	

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the frequency of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and its associated risk factors among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The findings

revealed a high frequency of NAFLD (60.2%) among diabetic patients, highlighting the substantial burden of this condition in the studied population. This is consistent with previous studies reporting NAFLD prevalence

ranging from 50% to 80% in patients with T2DM, confirming that diabetes is one of the strongest risk factors for hepatic steatosis [9].

The strong association between T2DM and NAFLD is explained by shared pathophysiological mechanisms, particularly insulin resistance, which plays a central role in the development of both conditions. Insulin resistance leads to increased lipolysis, free fatty acid influx into the liver, and subsequent triglyceride accumulation within hepatocytes. Additionally, chronic inflammation and oxidative stress further contribute to disease progression from simple steatosis to more advanced liver pathology [10].

In the present study, obesity emerged as a major risk factor, with a significantly higher proportion of NAFLD observed in obese individuals ($p < 0.001$). This finding is in line with existing literature, where obesity, especially central obesity, is considered a key determinant of NAFLD. Adipose tissue dysfunction leads to altered adipokine secretion and increased inflammatory mediators, which promote hepatic fat accumulation and insulin resistance [11]. The high prevalence of obesity among NAFLD patients in this study underscores the importance of weight management in preventing and controlling the disease.

Smoking was also found to be significantly associated with NAFLD in this study. Patients with a history of smoking had a higher frequency of NAFLD compared to non-smokers ($p < 0.001$). Smoking has been shown to exacerbate oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and systemic inflammation, all of which contribute to metabolic disturbances and liver injury. Recent studies have highlighted smoking as an independent risk factor for NAFLD and its progression to more severe forms [12].

Hypertension demonstrated a strong and statistically significant association with NAFLD ($p < 0.001$). This finding supports the concept that NAFLD is part of a broader metabolic syndrome spectrum, where hypertension coexists with insulin resistance and dyslipidemia. The presence of hypertension further increases cardiovascular risk in these patients, making NAFLD not only a hepatic condition but also a marker of systemic vascular disease [13].

Although NAFLD was more frequent in older patients and males, the association with age and gender was not statistically significant in this study. This contrasts with some international studies that report higher prevalence in older age groups and males. However, recent evidence suggests that these differences may be diminishing due to lifestyle changes, increasing obesity rates, and hormonal factors, particularly in postmenopausal women [14]. The lack of statistical significance in this study may also be attributed to sample size or population-specific characteristics.

No significant association was found between NAFLD and residence, education, employment status, or socioeconomic status. This suggests that NAFLD is becoming increasingly prevalent across all demographic groups, reflecting widespread exposure to metabolic risk factors. The traditional distinctions between urban and rural populations are becoming less pronounced due to globalization, dietary transitions, and sedentary lifestyles [15].

The diagnosis of NAFLD in this study was based on ultrasonography, which, although widely used and practical, has limitations in detecting mild steatosis and cannot assess fibrosis accurately. Recent guidelines recommend the use of non-invasive scoring systems and biomarkers, such as FIB-4 and transient elastography, to improve diagnostic accuracy and risk stratification [16,17]. Incorporating these tools in future studies may provide a more comprehensive assessment of disease severity.

Overall, the findings of this study highlight the high burden of NAFLD among patients with T2DM and its strong association with modifiable risk factors such as obesity, smoking, and hypertension. Early identification and targeted management of these risk factors are essential to prevent disease progression and reduce associated complications. Given the increasing prevalence of both T2DM and NAFLD, integrated screening and management strategies are crucial in clinical practice [18–20].

Limitations

This study had several limitations. Firstly, it was conducted at a single center, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Secondly, the cross-sectional design does not allow for

establishment of causal relationships. Thirdly, ultrasonography was used for diagnosis, which has limited sensitivity for detecting early or mild steatosis. Additionally, factors such as dietary habits, physical activity, and genetic predisposition were not assessed, which may influence the development of NAFLD. Future multicenter longitudinal studies with advanced diagnostic modalities are recommended for a more comprehensive evaluation.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates a high frequency of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, emphasizing its significant clinical burden. Obesity, smoking, and hypertension were found to be strongly associated risk factors, highlighting the role of modifiable determinants in disease development. These findings underscore the need for routine screening of NAFLD in diabetic patients and early intervention through lifestyle modification, optimal glycemic control, and management of cardiovascular risk factors to prevent disease progression and related complications.

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